

An Introspection of formulation of Urban Voids in highly urbanized Indian Cities

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Abstract. The United Nations has estimated that by 2050 around 50% of the Indian population will stay in urban areas. India's fastest-growing economy has led to a rampant influx of migrants from rural to urban areas much faster than projected resulting into alarming transformational impacts on urban land management, economic structure, environment, and socio-cultural life. To withstand this situation, the macro & micro-scaled Urban Renewal has become crucial and continual affair in Indian cities. However, several macro-scaled urban renewal projects have been futile as they have adapted the irrational clean slate approach with no connect to the very context.

On the other hand, there is a pressing need for micro-scale resurgence as these revivals adhere to the socio-cultural context and has a multiplier effect over the local economy. The study of such revival becomes essential as many parts of the urban Indian cities are unplanned and abruptly developed due to several reasons, creating more and more vacant, underutilized, odd land parcels called as Urban Voids which constitutes around 10-15% of the City area. The voids have impacted harshly on every aspect of city life diminishing our ethos, social character, and cultural setting. Nowadays, this has become an ordinary scenario in numerous highly dense cities of developing nations.

Thus, the research aims to introspect various such reasons of formulation of urban voids in Indian cities. Along with that, it also compares the difference between voids in cities having urban sprawl and highly dense cities. Further, the study asserts the necessity of micro-scaled renewal method based on the revival of Urban voids especially for the highly urbanized areas in the Indian context.

Keywords: Introspection, urban renewal, urban voids, highly urbanized cities, developing nation, India

1 Introduction

After the World wars, full-fledged demolition and reconstruction of cities became a topmost priority in the Western world, especially in US and UK. *“But, unlike their Western counterparts, Indian cities didn't have the fortune or misfortune of being de-*

molished in the world war. Most of the Indian cities are built in layers bearing testimony to various rulers during different periods and amalgamated to give the present shape” (Dhote, Silakri, & P, 2013).

However, it was the economic liberalization and globalization of the early '90s which resulted in shifting of the focus on 'Urban development' considering it as the engine of India's economic growth. Simultaneously, it encouraged the resurgence of several parts of the cities and triggered the transformations in the physical, social and economic structure of these cities. Furthermore, the necessity of such renewal projects arose significantly from land value increase, FSI or density increase, market pressure, need of new economic magnet, collapsed the local economy and many such other reasons. These causes affected the land management in multiple ways creating a strong need for the revival of lands, buildings, and infrastructure at all levels (Aruninta, 2005).

Also, the Indian Government has incorporated 'Urban Renewal' as a part of National Mission in the form of JNNURM (Jawaharlal Nehru National Urban Renewal Mission) and AMRUT (Atal Mission for Rejuvenation and Urban Transformation) to name a few. Nowadays, such renewal projects on either unused and underused lands have become prevalent in today's India which is in the phase of continuous change.

Nevertheless, many of the cases worldwide has also ascertained that the reuse of abandoned lands, derelict sites, vacant plots, brownfields and such other obsolete lands referred as 'Urban Voids' can become the catalyst for urban growth as these lands have tremendous development potential (Trancik, 1986). The underutilized and dilapidated lands and projects are generally taken into consideration for either redevelopment, refurbishment, and rehabilitation both at macro & micro scale.

2 Methodology

The sequential methodology mentioned here primarily differentiates between the cities having urban sprawl versus the highly dense cities. It conveys the obscurity within the study and subsequently diagnoses the prominent reasons of formulation of urban voids within the highly dense Indian cities. The study leads further to analyze the causes for failure of macro-scale urban renewal and its non-suitability in such highly dense cities. It further ascertains the need of micro-scaled urban void alleviation especially in the Indian context. Thus, overall discourse mentioned here is primarily based on various literature sources as well as procedural & policy approaches followed by archetypal Development Authorities from each zone of India for revival of urban voids considering the broad spectrum of urban renewal, which is discussed in further paragraphs.

3 Discussion & Analysis

3.1 The difference between Urban Voids in cities having Urban sprawl and Highly dense Cities

Before analyzing the urban voids in an Indian context, we need to understand that the urban void as a concept has been derived out of cities like Denver, Philadelphia, London, Sydney, Melbourne etc. having urban sprawl mostly belonging to developed nations like USA, UK, and Australia to name a few. Significantly, large voids in these cities are developed due to the infrastructural requirements and distantly placed land uses. The population in such cities is also very less comparatively.

Contrary to this, the voids in the highly dense cities of several Asian countries follow a different pattern of generation. Although these voids are small or medium in size fragmented in highly populated cities, they have a strong socio-cultural and economic association with the context. Redevelopment of these voids can immensely contribute to the microeconomic development as well as in fulfilling the infrastructural and societal needs.

The comparison between these two different models has been mentioned in Table 1 which sets the background for the need of study of urban voids in highly dense Indian cities further.

Table 1. Comparison between Voids in cities having urban sprawl and highly dense cities (Source: KIT,2015)

Voids in cities having Urban Sprawl (Exa: Denver, Philadelphia, London, Sydney, Melbourne etc.)	Voids in Highly dense Cities (Exa: Ahmedabad, Mumbai, Jaipur, Dhaka, Rangoon, Colombo etc.)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reasons of voids: Infrastructural voids & distantly placed land uses. • Use: Large reservations and acquisitions for Infrastructure projects like highways, loops, junctions, flyovers, parking etc. • Size: Voids are more in number & large in size. Large tracts of land available as void or abandoned sites, thus substantial land available for large projects under redevelopment. • Activity: Large land parcels used for illegal & criminal activities creating more unsafe and isolated zones. • Authority: Special Purpose vehicle addresses the administrative conflicts. • Focus: More concentration towards environmental concerns & economic gains. Safety, security & maintenance issues are profoundly taken into consideration. Environmental sustainability taken into consideration at all fronts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reasons of Voids: Voids are found where infrastructure is less and quality of life is deficient. Many lands available but have legal issues. • Use: Majorly for Reservations for open & green spaces, amenities & services. Small & Medium sized reservations, very difficult to get large plots for infrastructure projects. • Size: Voids are more in number but Small or Medium in size. Land parcels are fragmented. Cannot be combined for larger purpose. • Activity: Unused areas occupied illegally mainly by slums, criminal activities, vending or used to dump garbage • Authority: Urban renewal projects are tricky to work out as multiple authorities are involved. No single decision-making body to deal with such lands (Exclusions like NCRTDA, MMRDA etc.) • Focus: Economic gain overpowers on socio-cultural & environmental concerns which is the basis of society.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding: Enormous funds are available for renewal. • Framework: Clear policies available to deal with macro & micro renewal projects. Clarity in administrative set up – Better coordination due to uniform digital platform. • Community Participation: Active Community participation. Many small & medium projects initiated by community, PPP and also supported by government. • Points: High quality of life, less population and low built mass density but more sprawl, increasing the travel distance. • Need: Need to focus upon local or micro scaled economy & Socio-cultural issues. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding: Funds not available from govt. to develop large projects but they are raised either from international forums or Public-private partnerships. • Framework: No legal framework for Micro (Small & medium) scaled projects, thus no separate funds. No clear policies to deal with such lands. • Community Participation: Hardly any active community participation is observed. • Points: Average quality of life, more Population, highly dense settlements, encroachments on lands. • Need: Avoiding blindly copying from West, out of context designs, Socio-cultural setting disturbed as no connect with the society. Energy conscious refurbishment needed. If treated in well manner, may have positive effects on microclimate, microeconomy & society.
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3.2 Macro and micro level reasons for the formulation of urban voids in Indian context

A. Radical restructuring of Global Economy

Though the globalization and innovations have brought the world closer however considering the world-wide perspective, the author Saskia Sassen reveals that “*Transformations in the composition and locational patterns of the economy have assumed specific forms in cities and the urban hierarchy. The new service-dominated urbanization, particularly evident in major cities, has distinct consequences for a range of social conditions*” (Sassen, 1990).

Eventually, in India, one can see there is a radical shift from Agro-based economy to manufacturing sector and simultaneously from manufacturing to a service sector economy within the last 2 to 3 decades. This resulted into increasing market orientation, deregulation and privatization, the emergence of internationally competitive industrial and technical sectors and growing integration with the global economy, in conjunction with rapid economic growth and very considerable, growing disparity of poverty and wealth (Beale, 2017).

These transformations in the economy also brought abrupt changes in the land management and its distribution in the urban areas of India resulting into thousands of abandoned homes, unused buildings, and vacant lots, contributing to urban decay. These changes exasperate urban planning and revival, fostering deviance in the forms anti-social activities and vagrancy (Economic Restructuring, 2017). Ariya Aruninta has also pointed out a radical restructuring of the global economy in recent decades has resulted in an explosion in the number of Urban Voids and inefficient decision making, poor land management, poor co-ordination among decision-makers as the main policy problems that created Urban Voids (Aruninta, 2005).

B. Population Explosion and Rampant Urbanization

In 2050, India, the fourth fastest-growing economies will be home to 14% of the world's urban population. In less than thirty years, half of India's population will have to cope with urban life and there will be a tremendous transformation of a landscape, economic structure and social life (United Nations, 2012). Urbanization trend is seen all over the world but is becoming most dominant in Asia converting more towns into cities. The UN report has projected that about 50% of the Indian population will be staying in urban areas by 2050. Major Indian cities are among the fastest-growing in the world, including Bangalore, Ahmedabad, Hyderabad, Pune, Chennai, Delhi, and Mumbai (Jayanthi, 2018). The abrupt influx of migrants and increased land prices due to higher demand have pushed the population to stay in suburbs as well as in the fringes of the city. Such rampant influx provoked people to settle in unplanned fringes resulting in more odd & underused land parcels creating more voids.

Hereby, we can say that urbanization remains a predominant factor that is continuously linked to the destruction of old cultural & social spaces, green covers and open spaces in most of the Indian urban areas (Jayanthi, 2018). This, unfortunately, resulted in diminishing our ethos, social character and cultural setting especially in cosmopolitan Metros (Raisoni, 2018).

C. Spatial Growth: Uncontrolled Peri-urban development

Initially, several Indian cities were unplanned or planned without strong futuristic vision. Also, the spontaneous urbanization caused the wastage and destruction of natural resources especially the 'Urban Land'. *"The inappropriate use of land destroys the quality of the space in the city thus becoming a Lost Space or underutilized Space"* (Silva, 1998).

The outward expansion of larger metros, gradual changes in the land use and occupations have transformed the Indian rural hinterland into semi-urban or 'peri-urban' areas (Shaw, 2005). The continuous inflow of migrants every time pushes the city boundaries outside the capacity of the Urban Local Bodies. Thus, most of the peri-urban areas of many Indian cities are abruptly developed and lacks in basic amenities and recreational facilities, creating more and more lands vacant, underutilized or unassigned for the determined usage.

D. Planning & Procedural Issues

Even though we are planning urban areas thinking about every single conceivable projections, situations, and complexities, it takes a substantial amount of time to observe the outcomes. *"Traditional planning strategies, positioned within Modernist paradigms, required to resolve urban problems through methods of instrumental rationality"* (Wohl, 2017, p. 1). The reality of the matter is that transformative infrastructure and planning projects have their place; new frameworks like rail lines, bridges, public infrastructure, streets or the rezoning of a whole city are difficult, however positively vital and imperative activities.

The failure of these blueprints to accomplish wanted results, coupled with a general move far from modernist principles, has pushed planning towards more unpredictable,

reflective and unfavorable situations. *“These recognize the need to move beyond faith in master plans with their end-states, and instead acknowledge unknown, ambiguous futures that are often fragmented, relational, and complex”* (Boonstra B, 2011, pp. 99-122).

In India, it the reality of the matter that the rate of effective implementation of City/Regional level plans is far less than what it was conceived. Consequently, the fragmented city plans lead to the formulation of unconventional land parcels. Even the designer’s contribution becomes an after the fact cosmetic treatment of spaces that are ill-shaped and ill-planned for public use at the first place (Silva, 1998).

E. Conflicts in Policies / Inter-authoritative issues.

The typical planning process followed by many Indian cities is the top-down approach of planning which starts with Regional Plans, development plans and zonal development plans which follows a lengthy and tiresome process. Planning in India continues to be aggregative and sectoral, devoid of spatial dimensions. This makes the integration of plans at different levels and between different sectors very difficult (Minocha, 1983). In reality, the formulation, gazetting and implementation require more time than expected. In the whole process, many authorities have to deal with each other for better implementation but pragmatically, it involves conflicts in their policies and rights (Aruninta, 2005).

Every city in India is also facing the challenge of providing the compatible land-uses which demands the holistic sustainable development ideally. It is significant that the neighborhood-specific, block specific and finally the three-dimensional intimate scale planning is missing from Indian planning process which eventually diminishes attachment of citizens with the place. Monotonous, blindly imitated and isolated spaces are being planned without considering the three-dimensional relationship between the buildings and actual plots, human behavior, its context and demand of the citizens. The resultant of which is the creation of unused or underutilized land parcels and unshaped anti-spaces across the cities (Silva, 1998).

Rent control Act has not proved effective due to disconnect from urban reality. The experience with ULCRA has been similar. Lower FSI at many places has also created many void or underutilized spaces. Nowadays, Land Management through various mechanisms like TDR (Transfer of Development Rights), PPP (Public-Private Partnership) and TPS (Town Planning Schemes), etc. have indicated positive outcomes still a comprehensive outlook is needed in the practice.

F. Need of effective decision Making

Though the City planning is a comprehensive responsibility of multiple authorities, however, it also involves conflicts between various such landholding agencies. Many times, the infrastructure and development programs are reactionary, impulsive and not well thought of considering the future. Also, at many places, the planning and development processes are mainly driven by the influence of elite class and political will. The

change in the governments, poor conclusive decisions, facing undue pressures and interest of many stakeholders have majorly affected the planning process in many Indian Cities.

The limited capabilities of the Government sector and lack of coordination between multiple stakeholders in the planning process must result in the deterioration of urban environments in Indian cities. Also, the governments at Central, state and ULB level may not necessarily be of same political parties, resultant of which is the conflicts between decision making and implementation of the projects.

Similarly, it is significant that the public planning process has turned out to be ineffective on account of either government inaction, fewer finances, inaccessible resources or absence of consensus (Raisoni, 2018). The resultant of all these episodes is the creation of unutilized or underutilized public lands, enormous loss in community character, loss of vibrant urban spaces, heritage areas and majorly the community greens.

G. Speculative Lands & Legal issues

Many of the public lands have been found in disputes about the ownership rights as they have been occupied by non-government groups since a long period. Some of such matters are still under the legal purview and waiting for the decision of development. Likewise, many private lands also lying vacant or non-functional due to the disputes over property rights.

Around \$200 billion investment has been threatened due to conflicts over 2.5 million hectares of land affecting about 7.7 million people. Although the laws are clear and transparent, the administrative failure to comply with the rule of law by unwillingness and incapacity has resulted in the deceleration, pendency, and delay in resolving land conflicts (Wahi, 2019). Around 66% of litigations are land & property related. (Thakur, 2016).

Though, in many states, the Public Land Encroachment Act has been made to curtail illegal occupancy of the government lands, still the encroachments over public lands, incompatible spaces, large vacant public lands, obsolete buildings, slums, underutilized buildings, and natural barriers have created the ‘voids’ or ‘gaps’ between the Indian cities. The void disrupts the continuity of city fabric and various disjointed segments create a disorienting experience (Jayanthi, 2018).

H. Shortage of capital for the development & maintenance of serviced lands

The economic productivity of the cities is primarily decided by the development of infrastructure over the land. Significantly, the development of various public infrastructure projects has immediate effects on the encircling land values. *“Land values are highly sensitive to infrastructure investment and urban economic growth. Many cities in developing countries have underused public lands that would be more valuable if sold and converted into infrastructure assets.”* (Peterson, 2008). Available lands act as a valuable resource in generating & mobilizing the capital or revenues upfront (Ballaney, 2013).

The potential and the value of the land increases only if it has the provision of basic services like water supply, drainage, sewerage, electricity, etc. is available. The well-developed access road increases the land value multiple times. Shortage of basic minimum services, appropriate amenities and most essential the access roads, deteriorates the condition and reduces the market value of the land. Such lands either become obsolete or obscene because of inappropriate infrastructure.

After taking many precautionary measures during the planning process, many public lands are still vacant or underutilized. The key issue is with a lack of operational and maintenance costs. The Government agencies have limited capacity to deal with this intrinsic issue and lack the mechanism to map, analyze and resolve the issue of urban voids. Though some framework is given in the urban renewal policies, still comprehensive, meticulous and micro-level revival of such spaces is a major lacuna.

I. Other reasons

- *Lack of Community Participation*: The City planning has always been considered as people's prerogative where the common man is involved to induce and manage the city's activities. But in India, lack of awareness, belongingness, willingness and negligence of community are major reasons for limited Public participation during the planning process.
- *Inferior quality of land*: Within our city premises, the steeply sloped lands, water-logged areas, salty and marshy lands, brownfields, inaccessible lands, etc. has created voids because of its inferior quality thus, significantly locking the development potential of the same.
- *Underutilized lands for infrastructural projects / reserved land parcels*: Due to multiple factors discussed above, many of the lands reserved for public amenities & facilities and open & green spaces are still undeveloped or underdeveloped. Several lands acquired for various public purposes are still waiting for the green signal from government authorities or got developed halfway creating more voids.

Therefore, from overall discussion and analysis, we can infer that the concern of generation of urban voids has not been addressed holistically and the potential of '*urban regeneration through the development of urban voids*' is not well recognized in the Indian context. The existence of voids affects urban interactions and results in the formation of urban morphologies of non-potentiality for further development. Furthermore, several large-scale urban renewal projects have not been able to withstand the contextual setup as they were blindly cloned from the West, which is discussed further.

3.3 Failure of Macro-Scaled Urban Renewal in India

Though the macro urban renewal projects have a larger impact on the land use, density, population and economy over the context and sometimes overall city, however, they have been criticized for following a 'Clean Slate' approach as well as for not being responsive enough in the socio-cultural context of India. Sometimes such large projects

have failed to give the desired economic outputs as the considerations of local culture, socio-economic setups, community participation is not considered, thus becoming ‘Urban Bulldozers’ (Dhote, Silakri, & P, 2013). One of the major reasons may be the un-mindful replication of other similar projects but from different contextual setup. The affordability and feasibility of such projects have also remained a major reason for failure. The change in the governments, community issues, political will, interdepartmental issues, lobbying private developers, increasing costs due to the lengthy project durations have made these projects unsuccessful for a long run further discussed in Table 2.

Table 2. Table showing the positive and negative points about the Macro-scaled Urban Renewal

Positives of Macro-Scaled Urban Renewal	Negatives of Macro-Scaled Urban Renewal
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large obsolete lands can be effectively utilized. • City level revival of Infrastructure. • Planned better environment for part of the City. • More Tax revenue can be generated. • Current and future requirements can be planned in more effective way. • If the new project becomes suitable for context, it can bring an enormous positive change in the societal structure. • More open & public spaces can be generated. • Better chance of planning & reinforcing the well-structured infrastructure. • Private funding can be raised thus less economic burden on government. • Legal policy framework available for the said area. • Larger impact not only on city/immediate context but can have regional impact. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Old buildings get destroyed creating ill effects on Socio-Cultural setting of the city. Historical character of the city is at stake. • Economic output is less in many projects questioning the sustainability of the project. • Large impact on the context raising environmental concerns. • Burden on existing infrastructure. • In many cases community participation is not considered thus reduces attachment and sense of belongingness. • Mere copying from West. Sensitive planning considering local context is insignificant resulting in failure of the project. • Affordability & feasibility is in question. • Micro scale renewal is not considered thus macro project may prove to be alien in the context. • Multiple stakeholders, political will and change in governments puts project’s future at stake. • Raising the funds becomes an issue for government. • Lack of unanimous decisions • Lobbying of private developers compromising on the quality. • Lengthy project durations thus involves more cost – Less projects can be executed within designated time • Stringent laws – Not flexible- Less resilient – Not so easy to implement – Static in nature • Development in isolation

In contrast to this, the micro-scaled urban renewal initiatives for obsolete sites are still missing from Indian Town Planning processes. We know that a city can’t respond to all its predicaments just by preparing the wholesome plans; it ought to moreover move quickly on numerous diminutive planning processes (Raisoni, 2018). Certainly, these are the ones that embrace the citizens and usually have a remarkable effect on community space character as time goes on. In short, urban neighborhoods not only demand oversized plans but micro-scaled interventions as well, which will transform that particular void area. If many such areas in the city get alleviated, automatically a

city will advance in a multifold pattern, Thus, the need of such micro-scaled renewal method based on a revival of urban voids will be discussed further.

3.4 The necessity of Micro-scaled renewal based on the revival of Urban voids in Indian cities

The following points conveys the necessity of Micro-scaled resurgence based on revival of Urban voids for highly densed Indian cities

A. Resilient & Sustainable micro scaled urban renewal is required.

The conventional methods of upgrading the urban areas by demolishing the entire districts to provide space for new constructions & skyscrapers are increasingly found to be no longer up to date & sustainable (KIT, 2015). Funding to such large projects is also a major concern. Large scaled renewal projects add on more population but the city infrastructure is not capable of handling the additional load. Therefore, the highly dense cities, especially in the Indian context, requires micro-scaled urban renewal initiatives which are resilient, comprehensive, community friendly and sustainable.

B. Need of Framework for the identification and Assessment of Voids

After analyzing several Government Acts, policies and programs, it has observed that Indian cities need the Framework to identify, analyze and resolve the issues of urban void spaces. Many cities also need the study of the factors which has generated the void spaces in the urban areas. Neighborhood scale and intimate scale spaces which remain untreated thus encroached upon need more attention. Such sights have become a blight and create a negative image of the city on a global platform. Hence, one can say that, our cities need a holistic perspective to evaluate the potentials of each Urban Void as per the need of its context (Silva, 1998).

C. Necessity of study of impacts of voids on immediate urban realm

Though the urbanization of our cities has created many positive impacts on the development, the voids created by urbanization has severely affected the immediate urban realm. Deficiency of recreational spaces and public greens within reach has also affected the social and cultural settings of our cities. Therefore, an impact analysis or vulnerability analysis of voids over its immediate urban realm is significantly needed.

D. Need of balance between Socio-Cultural & Environmental Aspects

The fast pace of urbanization is continuously linked to the destruction of old cultural & social spaces, green covers and open areas in most of the Indian cities. "Cities without Memories" is seen to be followed by many cities. Also, the uncontrolled and haphazard development has a tremendous ill effect on our environment which in India is adulated once upon a time. Hence, the sustainability of any revival will be majorly dependent on the ultimate balance of Social, Cultural & environmental aspects of the Society.

E. Requirement of an Integrated Authority

The conflict between the territories of multiple authorities has fragmented the land parcels in our cities, which in turn gets converted into isolated blank spaces. Though we have a framework for Urban Renewal, it only considers the projects of large scale and in isolation. Redevelopment of such parcels may result in the betterment of that particular site only. But practical experiences in India has proved that such projects lack

the multiplier effect in face-lifting our cities in a holistic manner. Thus, an integrated authority will be able to minimize the conflicts between various stakeholders creating more efficient, uniform, expeditious, appropriate and comprehensive decision making for the city level revival of urban voids.

Ultimately, after analyzing urban voids in multi-dimensions, one can say that, there is a strong need of several micro-scaled urban renewal initiatives based on a revival of urban voids instead of few disoriented macro-scaled urban renewal projects which are alien in context.

4 Conclusions

The introspective study of urban voids in highly dense cities of India is far more different than its Western counterparts, thus requires serious attention of government and planners in formulating a strategic model in developing these voids. In India, the reasons for formulation of voids are unique, multidimensional and complex, therefore, they need to be handled by proposing a Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV) at regional or city level, who will address all sorts of concern and resolve the disputes between multiple stakeholders for the better & sustainable growth of the community. The small & medium-sized unused or underutilized blight spots will need a separate policy framework and multi-layered plans under Urban Renewal Regulations but shall be handled by the SPV. This authority needs to carry out physical & visual surveys across the gamut of the city for identifying & defining voids as well as evaluating the factors generating them. After such a diagnosis, it will give a holistic perspective at city level about the potential of each void and then its improvised usage for the community can be defined.

Involvement of various stakeholders, majorly the Community participation will create a movement in face-lifting the local area around the void. The collective efforts to generate the funds partially from Central or state government, ULBs, private players and community will assist in redefining the 'Urban Void' to 'Urban Catalyst'. The comprehensive efforts put by all the players will revive many parts of the city by appropriate acupuncture, catalyzing the local economy, improving the socio-cultural ties between the community and boosting tourism. Such kind of study in the Indian context will provide orientation for the similar highly dense cities falling across the Asian continent.

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